

ORGANIZATIONAL MECHANISMS OF THE TRANSITION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES TO THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

Kurbanova Rakhima¹

Khakimov Damir²

PhD, senior lector , Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service
Student of Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service

Abstract. *In this article, because of the continuous quarantine in the context of the 2020 pandemic, many businesses have suffered huge losses and were forced to lay off their employees. However, even in such conditions, there were those who did not stop their activities, at least partially, changing their business from the traditional to the online method, using the available electronic resources at the enterprise. We focused on studying the organizational and economic issues of the transition of service enterprises to the digital economy and developing proposals for them. The issues of creating local digital platforms of a different level of digital technologies, as well as the need to create a server for organizations and enterprises that are its source are consider*

Keywords: *Digital economy, platform, server, generation, electronic*

1.INTRODUCTION

It is known that service enterprises include: catering (restaurants, kitchens, cafes, bars, etc.), hotels (hotels, botels, hostels, etc.), trade (shops, stores, mini-, supermarkets, hypermarkets)) and enterprises that meet the needs of other consumers. The share of services in GDP in 2019 is 35.5%, including the share of services and other types of services - 20.9%, transportation and storage, information and communication - 7.7%, trade, accommodation and catering - 6 , 9%³.

As a result of the uninterrupted quarantine during the 2020 pandemic, many businesses suffered heavy losses and were forced to lay off their employees. However, even in such circumstances, there were those who did not stop their activities, albeit partially, by changing their business activities from the traditional

¹ PhD, senior lector , Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service

² Student of Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service

³ <https://stat.uz/uploads/doklad/2019/yanvar-dekabr/uz/1.pdf>

method to the online method, using the available electronic resources in the enterprise. At the same time, they continued to provide pre-order food, ready meals and other services to the address indicated by the residents or at their request. But even then, it was difficult to get the products needed for business needs. Similarly, due to weak external relations and underdeveloped service infrastructure, the company currently faces obstacles in selling or leasing fixed assets. At the same time, the lack of a database of enterprises makes this process inefficient. In our opinion, the main solution is to transfer all enterprises to the digital economy. As the President said: “uchun It is necessary and necessary to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies in order to achieve development. This allows us to take the shortest path to ascension... .No matter how difficult it is, if we don't start this work today, when will we start ?! It will be too late tomorrow. Therefore, the active transition to the digital economy will be one of our priorities for the next 5 years First of all, construction, energy, agriculture and water management, transport, geology, cadastre, health, education, archives will be fully digitized. Also, the "e-government system ..." ⁴ complex solution. But that doesn't mean others have to sit back and watch the gradual transition to a digital economy using the resources available from now on. Suggestions on methods of digitization of services In the works of Gulyamov S.S.⁵, Yu.I.Gribanov^{6,7}, the digitization of sectors of the economy and its contribution to the competitiveness of enterprises Skrug V.S.⁸, Babkin A.V⁹ and in the studies of others.

⁴ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis “Zarafshon” newspaper, January 25, 2020, No. 10-11, page 4.

⁵ Gulyamov S.S. and others. Blockchain technologies in the digital economy. T .: Iqtisod Molia, 2019. 396 p

⁶ Gribanov Yu.I. Methodology of economic development, promyshlennosti i sfery uslug v usloviyax tsifrovizatsii: kollektivnaya monografiya / Yu.I. Gribanov, under ed. A.V. Babkina. SPb .: Politekh-Press, 2018. S. 48-90.

⁷ Gribanov Yu.I. Basic model creation otraslevykh digital platform / Yu.I. Gribanov // Voprosy innovatsionnoy ekonomiki. - 2018. - Tom 8. № 2. - S.223-234. - 1.1 p.l.

⁸ Skrug V.S. Transformation of industrialization in digital economy: problems and perspectives // Creative economy. - 2018. - Tom 12. - № 7. - S. 943-952. doi: 10.18334 / ce.12.7.39208

⁹ Babkin A.V., Chistyakova O.V. Tsifrovaya ekonomika i ee vliyanie na konkurentosposobnost predprinimatelskix struktura // Rossiyskoe predprinimatelstvo. - 2017. - Volume 18. - № 24. - p. 40874102. doi: 10.18334 / rp.18.24.38670

Based on the findings of the literature, we focused our research on the study of organizational and economic issues of the transition of service enterprises (catering and housing and sales) to the digital economy and the development of proposals on them. It is necessary to create local, other-level digital platforms of digital technology, as well as to create a server of organizations, enterprises, which are its source.

II. THE MAIN PART

Research Methods In the study, we used the methods of "System Analysis" and "Logical Analysis". Although there is no definitive definition of the digital economy in the world today^{10,11} given that it is an activity on the creation, distribution and use of digital technologies and related products and services, digitization of service enterprises (processes of electronic collection, storage, processing, transmission and presentation¹² of information) means primarily the generation of enterprise).

During the generation process, information about the business processes in the enterprise is digitized or converted into a number form. To do this, it is advisable to use the existing electronic equipment in the enterprise (their classification is shown in Figure 1). They are: IBM, Xerox, Toshiba, Siemens, Epson, Canon, Panasonic, the information about which is given in our textbook¹³. During the pandemic period of our research, we used Samarkand-based Obi-Rakhmat LLC (Yulduz Restaurant and Shopping Center) and other enterprises to connect to future local or inter-sectoral digital platforms, digitize or digitize information about enterprise processes. using, we proposed to set up a single server

¹⁰Voloshin, A.V. Obzor podkhodov k opredeleniyu sushchnosti tsifrovoy ekonomiki / Ekonomicheskiiy mechanism kak instrument povysheniya effektivnosti deyatel'nosti predpriyatiy: sb. nauch. state / FGAOU «Siberian Federal University», 2019.-342 p.

¹¹Golovenchik G. Theoretical approaches to the definition of the concept of digital economy // Science and innovation. 2019. №1. S. 54 - 59. <https://doi.org/10.29235/1818-9857-2019-1-54-59>

¹² Abdrazmanova G. I. , Vishnevskiy K. O. , Goxberg L. M. and dr. ; nach. Red Goxberg, L. M. ; What is the digital economy? Trends, competencies, change. Nats. issled. un-t «Vysshaya shkola ekonomiki». - M. : Izd. house Vysshey school of economics, 2019. - 82, [2] p. - 250 copies.

¹³Kurbonov J.M., Kurbonova R.J. Electronic equipment of service enterprises.-Tashkent: Publisher, 2019. -168 p.

and use it to establish some external connections. In Samarkand city "Obi-Rahmat" LLC ("Yulduz" restaurant and shopping center), currently a total of 2 POS-systems, 12 electronic cash registers, 8 electronic scales and 3 personal computers are all connected to the HPE ProLiant DL120 Gen9 server. ulandi. At the same time, the existing electronic scales VE-15T at the enterprise were connected to the electronic cash register using special cables with plugs ONTs-VG -4-5 / 16 V and Sh N-1-5. POS-systems, cash registers based on the fiscal registrar, are part of a complex system that operates only on a computer-cash system, receiving information from the communication network.

Figure 1. Classification of electronic equipment of service enterprises.

While they work mainly on magnetic card payment, the speed is also adapted to the smart card and PIN PAD. They have available ports: 2xRJ-11 2/6 port (for telephone line and telephone), 1xRJ-11 4/4 port to connect PIN PAD (RS-232), 1xRJ-45 port for RS-232; for the battery, the modem is equipped with a 14400 bit / sec, smart card receiver and a 32-bit processor, a RAM disk that protects the data. In addition to connecting various peripherals to the POS-system BEETLEPOS-K, you can connect the cash terminal with the "local" communication network with the workplace of the sales hall manager in the administration and use it to monitor the movement of goods, balance, sales control, daily revenue, and other tasks. The company's SAMSUNGER 4615RF electronic cash register is also multifunctional, equipped with a convenient interior for communication between different networks (cash register, section, kitchen, administration, etc.) and access to personal computers or electronic scales with RS-232 interface. possible. Based on these electronic techniques, the programs "Profi-T", "Barcode-M: Cashier", "Frontol", "Advanced Stores Retail" are used. The enterprise-acquired HPEP ro Liant DL120 Gen9 Serverixcham 1U chassis and Intel® Xeon® E5-2600v3 / v4 or E5-1600v3 / v4 processor for high performance efficiency, clocked at 2400 MHz, with a maximum capacity of 256 GB. With the help of a single system in this created enterprise, the enterprise operates by launching many of the above-mentioned additional services. A similar system was proposed to be installed in the shopping center and kitchen of Urgut Fayz Savdo LLC in Urgut and in Juma Fayz LLC in Juma, but due to the small capacity of these enterprises and the lack of available electronic equipment, a larger personal computer was used instead of a server computer. . In addition to internal management and control, the company has the opportunity to communicate externally, and many additional services and other work is carried out. In general, the efficiency of the enterprise increased by an average of 14 - 17%.

III.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the above methodology, the transition to the digital economy was recommended in hotels in Samarkand. It was also argued that hotels could be integrated into existing HRS systems using the Fidelio and Micros software systems. Similarly, with the standard hotel automation complex (ABT) developed by the Russian company Rexsoft, all sections and subdivisions of the hotel (reception and accommodation of guests, booking via the Internet, warehouse, software for accounting, restaurant and bar, banquet service, technical department, sales and marketing, etc.). Using the above, it has been shown that in service enterprises: automatic management systems can dramatically increase the efficiency of enterprises (20-25%) by protecting investments and effective management, planning and reducing losses, providing various new additional services, connecting to different digital platforms in general.

IV.CONCLUSION

Based on the research, it was determined that it is expedient to gradually transfer service enterprises in Uzbekistan to the digital economy:

In the first stage, a digital technology base will be created for the organization of server systems in service enterprises; creates and puts into operation the basis for the organization of digital platforms at the local, intersectoral, national and international levels;

In Phase II, support mechanisms will be developed and put into practice to encourage the establishment of enterprises on the basis of incentives for access to digital platforms, to establish contacts at the national and international levels;

In the third stage, the transition of enterprises to the digital economy, the full use of national and international systems will be achieved.

REFERENCES

1. <https://stat.uz/uploads/doklad/2019/yanvar-dekabr/uz/1.pdf>
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis “Zarafshon” newspaper, January 25, 2020, No. 10-11, page 4.

3. Gulyamov S.S. and others. Blockchain technologies in the digital economy. T. : Iqtisod Molia, 2019. 396 p
4. Griбанov Yu.I. Methodology of economic development, promyshlennosti i sfery uslug v usloviyax tsifrovizatsii: kollektivnaya monografiya / Yu.I. Griбанov, under ed. A.V. Babkina. SPb. : Politex-Press, 2018. S. 48-90.
5. Griбанov Yu.I. Basic model creation otraslevykh digital platform / Yu.I. Griбанov // Voprosy innovatsionnoy ekonomiki. - 2018. - Tom 8. № 2. - S.223-234. - 1.1 p.l.
6. Skrug V.S. Transformation of industrialization in digital economy: problems and perspectives // Creative economy. - 2018. - Tom 12. - № 7. - S. 943-952. doi: 10.18334 / ce.12.7.39208
7. Babkin A.V., Chistyakova O.V. Tsifrovaya ekonomika i ee vliyanie na konkurentosposobnost predprinimatelskix struktura // Rossiyskoe predprinimatelstvo. - 2017. - Volume 18. - № 24. - p. 40874102. doi: 10.18334 / rp.18.24.38670
8. Voloshin, A.V. Obzor podkhodov k opredeleniyu sushchnosti tsifrovoy ekonomiki / Ekonomicheskiy mekhanizm kak instrument povыsheniya effektivnosti deyatel'nosti predpriyatiy: sb. nauch. state / FGAOU «Siberian Federal University», 2019.-342 p.
9. Golovenchik G. Theoretical approaches to the definition of the concept of digital economy // Science and innovation. 2019. №1. S. 54 - 59. <https://doi.org/10.29235/1818-9857-2019-1-54-59>
10. <https://investruture.ru/edu/artices/tsifrovaya-ekonomika-v-rossii>
11. Abdraxmanova G. I. , Vishnevskiy K. O. , Goxberg L. M. and dr. ; nauch. Red Goxberg. L. M. ; What is the digital economy? Trends, competencies, change. Nats. issled. un-t «Vysshaya shkola ekonomiki». - M. : Izd. house Vysshey school of economics, 2019. - 82, [2] p. - 250 copies.
12. Kurbonov J.M., Kurbonova R.J. Electronic equipment of service enterprises.- Tashkent: Publisher, 2019. -168 p.